

Advanced secured ATM system with three layer security protection

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ABSTARCT

The security of automated teller machine (ATM) transactions can be further strengthened using the three-level authentication system where the user is authenticated with what he has (ATM card), what he knows (personal identification number (PIN)) and what he is (fingerprint biometrics). The aim of the paper is to introduce a system where the ATM authenticates and verifies the true identity of the user. The use of fingerprint biometric in conjunction with existing authentication methods will eradicate fraudulent act and improve effective ATM transactions. The fingerprint concept is chosen because of its uniqueness with high level of accuracy, reliable and affordable. The paper, therefore, describes the simulation of an ATM with the capability of the combination of card, PIN and fingerprint biometrics based authentication with a view to provide a more reliable online banking transaction on ATM.

INTRODUCTION

The security level in the Automated Teller Machine (ATM) would not be hundred percent guaranteed provided there is no special way to identify who is banking at any point in time. One of the most effective ways of identifying and distinguishing between persons through traits is the use of biometrics. Biometrics is a rapidly advancing field that is concerned with identifying a person based on his or her physiological or behavioral characteristics (Rasu et al, 2012). Fingerprint technology in particular, can provide a much more accurate and reliable user authentication method. An important issue when considering biometric technology is to address the distinct classifications formally defined through application and implementation. As the ATM technology is advancing, fraudsters are devising different skills to beat the security of ATM operations. Various forms of fraud are perpetuated, ranging from: ATM card theft, skimming, pin

theft, card reader techniques, pin pad techniques, force withdrawals and lot more. Managing the risk associated with ATM fraud as well as diminishing its impact is an important issue that faces financial institutions as fraud techniques have become more advanced with increased occurrences. Considering the numerous security challenges encountered by ATM users and observing the existing security in the ATM system, there is the need to enhance the ATM security system to overcome these challenges. This study focuses on how to enhance security of transacting with ATM system using fingerprint technologies (Roli et al, 2011). Current security implementation does not proffer the adequate security necessary to secure electronic transactions, customers' information and funds (Falaye, 2013). It is therefore suggested that future work be done on the technical implementation of a more secured authentication method such as fingerprint technology and facial recognition. The major concern of Madu and Madu (2002) is about bank users' security and privacy while using the service of the ATM. Obiano (2009) blamed the menace of ATM frauds on indiscriminate issue of ATM card without regard to the customer's literacy level.

LITERATURE SURVEY

- **Adeloye, L.A (2008). “E-banking as new frontiers for banks”. Sunday punch, September 14, P.25.**

Electronic banking frauds are becoming a global phenomenon in nature, while its consequences are becoming a great concern for the banks worldwide. This paper tries to investigate the magnitude of online banking frauds in Nigerian commercial banks and proffer lasting solutions that will mitigate this contending and boiling issue in the Nigerian banking industry. The paper employs both primary and secondary data in order to investigate the online banking frauds in Nigerian banks. The chi-square statistical technique was used to analyze the data and test the hypothesis raised. The paper concludes that both bank customers and bankers have a joint role to play in stopping the perpetrators of online banking frauds in the banks. The research reveals that phishing attacks appear to be the dominant dimension of online banking frauds in Nigeria followed by fake web site substitution and pharming. While, vishing fraud is

not a common phenomenon in Nigeria, it ranked lowest in the ranking of the dimensions.

- **Cynthia B. (2000). “The measurement of white-collar crime using Uniform Crime Reporting”. (UCR) Data, Department of Justice, Federal Bureau of Investigation, New York.**

Extensive studies and research have been conducted on insider threats, the possible causes, predictive models and best practices for prevention, early detection, and mitigation of the threats of insider attacks to a wide range of critical infrastructure, government agencies, and the private sector. Current research shows a great deal of attention directed at the cyber threats toward organizations. In contrast, relatively little research has been conducted on the insider threat with regard to financial fraud and embezzlement to organizations. Left undetected, insiders can cause irreparable and devastating consequences to private and public sector organizations, which compromise the integrity of the overall financial system. **Falaye, A.A (2013). “A Survey of ATM Security**

Implementation within the Nigerian Banking Environment”.*Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce.*

This research work reviews the current practices in Nigeria’s customer banking services with an empirical investigation into ATM fraud as well as a physical and technical implementation of security. The survey was conducted using questionnaire as the research instrument. Four hundred 400 questionnaires were distributed among Entrepreneurs, Civil servants and Students from four states of the federation namely Lagos, Abuja, Kaduna and Jos. Three hundred and twenty seven (327) were retrieved successfully while three hundred and three (303) were properly responded. The data collected was analyzed using Chi-Square test and one way ANOVA. The results obtained shows there is no statistically significant difference in the perception of entrepreneurs, civil servants and students on the positive impact of ATM on banking. The perceptions of the three variables on security challenges of ATM services are

equal. It was concluded in the research that the current security implementation does not proffer the adequate security necessary to secure electronic transactions, customers' information and funds. The continuous advances in internet technology characterized by a complex and competitive environment have brought huge impact on business operations and have in particular brought about a paradigm shift in banking operations.

Gorman L. O. (1998). "Overview of fingerprint verification technologies". Elsevier Information Security Technical Report, vol. 3, no. 1.

Biometric as the science of recognizing an individual based on his or her physical or behavioral traits, it is beginning to gain acceptance as a legitimate method for determining an individual identity. Biometric have now been deployed in various commercial, civilian, and national security applications. Biometric described overview of various biometric techniques and the need to be addressed form making biometric technology an effective

tool for providing information security. Biometric recognition technology to use the problem of information security entails the protection of information elements (e.g., digital data) to access authorized users only. The content owners, such as authorized users, are losing billions of dollars annually due to the illegal copying and sharing of digital media. In order to address the growing problem, digital rights management (DRM) system are being deployed to regulate the duplicate data of digital content. The critical component of a DRM system is user authentication which determines whether a certain individual is indeed authorized to access the content available in a particular digital medium. To solve this problem lot of authentication technique is available. In a generic cryptographic system, the user authentication method is possession based

EXISTING SYSTEM

existing ATM systems have incorporated several security measures to protect against fraud, unauthorized access, and data

breaches. Physical security features include robust enclosures and tamper detection mechanisms to prevent unauthorized access and tampering. Many ATMs also employ secure card readers to mitigate the risk of card skimming, and some have started integrating biometric authentication methods, such as fingerprint scanning, to enhance user identification. Data security in existing ATM systems often involves end-to-end encryption for secure data transmission between the ATM and the banking network. Additionally, secure communication protocols and encryption standards are commonly employed to protect sensitive information, including PINs and transaction details. Transaction security is typically enforced through static PINs, and some systems have adopted dynamic authentication methods, such as one-time passwords (OTPs) or mobile authentication, to add an extra layer of security. Anomaly detection systems are in place to monitor transactions in real-time, triggering alerts for suspicious activities. While existing systems have implemented multi-layered security, ongoing efforts are made to address emerging threats. Regular software updates and security patches are crucial to maintaining the resilience of these systems. User education programs emphasize best practices, urging customers to safeguard

their PINs, be vigilant against skimming devices, and report any unusual activities. It's essential to note that the landscape of ATM security is dynamic, and financial institutions continually adapt their systems to respond to evolving cybersecurity threats. Checking with relevant financial institutions or industry reports for the latest advancements and security features in existing ATM systems would provide the most up-to-date information

PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed advanced ATM system aims to elevate security standards by implementing a comprehensive three-layer security architecture, ensuring a resilient defense against various threats. In the physical security layer, cutting-edge biometric authentication methods such as palm vein recognition and facial recognition will be introduced, enhancing user identity verification. The secure cash dispensing mechanism will undergo further enhancement, incorporating additional layers of authentication to authorize cash transactions exclusively for authenticated users. Geo-fencing technology will be integrated to bolster physical security, enabling immediate alerts and automatic disabling of the ATM if any unauthorized

movement or relocation is detected. The data security layer will feature advanced encryption protocols, ensuring end-to-end protection for data transmitted between the ATM and the banking network. Additionally, a secure enclave for storing sensitive information will be implemented, safeguarding against unauthorized access. The card reader will utilize dynamic tokenization for an added layer of security, replacing actual cardholder information with unique tokens, thereby mitigating risks associated with card skimming devices. In the transaction security layer, a dynamic multi-factor authentication system will be introduced, requiring users to authenticate transactions using a combination of factors such as biometrics, PINs, and one-time passwords. An advanced anomaly detection system, powered by machine learning algorithms, will monitor transactions in real-time, promptly identifying and responding to any suspicious activities. Regular software updates and security patches will be integral to the system's resilience, addressing emerging threats and vulnerabilities. User education programs will be implemented to raise awareness about the enhanced security features and promote best practices for safe ATM usage. The proposed system seeks to not only meet current security standards but

also anticipate and adapt to future challenges, providing a secure and trustworthy banking experience for users. Regular security audits and collaboration with cybersecurity experts will be crucial for the ongoing refinement and optimization of the proposed system.

BLOCK DIAGRAM

HARDWARE COMPONENTS

LCD (Liquid Cristal Display)

Introduction:

A liquid crystal display (LCD) is a thin, flat display device made up of any number of color or monochrome pixels arrayed in front of a light source or reflector. Each pixel consists of a column of liquid crystal molecules suspended between two transparent electrodes, and two polarizing filters, the axes of polarity of which are perpendicular to each other. Without the

liquid crystals between them, light passing through one would be blocked by the other. The liquid crystal twists the polarization of light entering one filter to allow it to pass through the other.

A program must interact with the outside world using input and output devices that communicate directly with a human being. One of the most common devices attached to a controller is an LCD display. Some of the most common LCDs connected to the controllers are 16x1, 16x2 and 20x2 displays. This means 16 characters per line by 1 line 16 characters per line by 2 lines and 20 characters per line by 2 lines, respectively.

Fingerprint scanner

People have patterns of [friction ridges](#) on their fingers, these patterns are called the [fingerprints](#). Fingerprints are uniquely detailed, durable over an individual's lifetime, and difficult to alter.^[5] Due to the unique combinations, fingerprints have become an ideal means of identification.^[6]

There are four types of fingerprint scanners:^[7] [optical scanners](#), capacitance scanners, ultrasonic scanners, and [thermal](#)

[scanners](#). The basic function of every type of scanner is to obtain an image of a person's fingerprint and find a match for it in its [database](#). The measure of the fingerprint image quality is in [dots per inch](#) (DPI).^[8]

1. **Optical scanners** take a visual image of the fingerprint using a digital camera.
2. **Capacitive or CMOS scanners** use capacitors and thus electric current to form an image of the fingerprint. This type of scanner tends to excel in terms of precision.
3. **Ultrasonic fingerprint scanners** use high frequency sound waves to penetrate the epidermal (outer) layer of the skin.
4. **Thermal scanners** sense the temperature differences on the contact surface, in between fingerprint ridges and valleys.

All fingerprint scanners are susceptible to be fooled by a technique that involves photographing fingerprints, processing the photographs using special software, and printing fingerprint replicas using a 3D

printer.^[9]

RFID READER

Active RFID and Passive RFID technologies, while often considered and evaluated together, are fundamentally distinct technologies with substantially different capabilities. In most cases, neither technology provides a complete solution for supply chain asset management applications. Rather, the most effective and complete supply chain solutions leverage the advantages of each technology and combine their use in complementary ways. This need for both technologies must be considered by RFID standards initiatives to effectively meet the requirements of the user community.

CONCLUSION

An enhanced security system if implemented with the use of fingerprint authentication in today's banking services will go a long way to eradicate all forms of financial misconduct

trailing our banking sector, since no two persons have the same fingerprint and will help to maintain accurate and a secured banking transaction. Traditional ATM systems authenticate generally by using the ATM card and the PIN method has some defects. Using ATM card and PIN only cannot verify the user's identity exactly. In recent years, the research on the fingerprint recognition is embedded into the system in order to offer new verification means for us. The original PIN authentication method combined with the biometric identification technology verify the users' identity better and achieve the purpose that use of ATM machines improve the safety effectively.

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